

THE SCIENCE OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY THROUGH MEDIA EDUCATION PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF DEVELOPING THE INFORMATION-ANALYTICAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHER

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Abstract: In the article, the effectiveness of multimedia lessons, the factors of positive influence on the development of informational and analytical competence of future teachers of technology are studied. Based on the scientific and practical significance of the article, suggestions and recommendations are given in the concluding part.

Key words: media education, media tool, multimedia, technology, analytical thinking, media literacy.

INTRODUCTION

Informatization of modern society, active use of information and telecommunication technologies in the educational system are the main reasons and relevance of increasing the attention of the informational-analytical competence of future technology teachers to media-educational issues.

The importance of media education and its support has been mentioned several times in UNESCO decisions and recommendations. According to UNESCO's 2002 recommendations, "media education is part of the basic right of every citizen to freedom of speech and information and contributes to the support of democracy. Recognizing the differences in the approaches and development of media education in different countries, it should be implemented as part of national curricula as much as possible, as well as in additional, non-formal education and self-education throughout a person's life. it is recommended to do so".[1]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Media education in the world is being updated and improved day by day. This is undoubtedly related to the rapid development of technologies, and people, especially young people, cannot imagine their behavior and life without media (internet). The activeness of students in classes and their interest in subjects and mastery of topics largely depends on the extensive use of multimedia by teachers. The use of multimedia projects not only makes the lesson visual and interesting, but also helps to influence the personal direction of a person.

Large-scale reforms in the field of education are being carried out in our country. The attention of our country to the field of education is high, especially in recent years, we witness every day that intensive education policy and reforms are being carried out. Human interests, the development of our country, and the development of future generations into worthy professions are envisaged in the framework of the reforms, and it is worth noting that the ongoing work has begun to show its results.

In educational reforms, we can see that goals and tasks are being set for the use of mass media in higher education institutions, especially multimedia and various other mass media. In particular, about 10 of the 100 goals (41, 50, 70, 71, 72, 76, 78, 82, 89 and for other

purposes) important works that provide for the relationship of young people with the media are defined.[2]

In addition, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 08.10.2019 No. PF-5847 "On the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", higher education institutions are provided with modern ICT tools. and provision of computer equipment, including the step-by-step purchase of computers, servers, wireless network equipment, projectors and multimedia equipment, as well as the task of developing and implementing databases and information systems in higher education institutions based on uniform requirements was loaded. [3] Studies on the use of multimedia for education conducted in our country show that more positive results have been observed in the development of informational-analytical competence of students who combine pictures and words than those who use only words. In particular, the effect of developing the informational-analytical competence of technology teachers on the basis of multimedia tools is twice as effective and time-saving as compared to the traditional method. It is possible to save up to 30% of time in learning based on multimedia tools, and the acquired knowledge is retained in the memory for a long time. If future technology teachers accept the given materials on the basis of viewing, memory retention of information and development of information-analytical competence will increase by 25-30%. In addition, when educational materials are presented in the form of audio, video and graphics, retention of materials increases by 75%.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

According to experts, media education teaches students to think independently, to further develop their creative activities, to receive information, to process it, to generalize, and to draw conclusions. The more perfect media education is in the educational process, the more it serves the development of the worldview and intellectual potential of the young generation. Therefore, today it is appropriate to study the secrets of media education in theory and apply them sufficiently in practice. In the conditions of globalization of information communication, specific requirements are emerging in the educational process. These requirements are closely related to media education.

Media education serves to raise the quality of all educational spheres to a higher level, to improve information culture. That is, future teachers of technology will have the opportunity to demonstrate the materials using high-level modern technology while providing theoretical knowledge in the educational process. This is a new and, so to speak, advanced method that arouses interest among students. They serve to thoroughly master those topics during the lesson.

According to the sources, on March 1, 1973, the International Council for Film and Television under UNESCO defined video education as follows: "Media education is the formation of theoretical and practical skills to acquire mass communication tools, which are considered as a special field of knowledge in the theory and practice of pedagogy. it is necessary to understand". [4]

Although sufficient legal frameworks and state programs have been adopted for the introduction of media education in the field of education, and local scientific studies have confirmed its usefulness and effectiveness, the factors for the development of informational and analytical competence of future teachers of technology Determining the true nature of

pedagogical knowledge and skills necessary for successful learning and educational activities is of urgent importance.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that research conducted in the world and in our country shows that educational policies and practices, media literacy are increasing in importance day by day with the incredible speed of communication technologies that are updating themselves every day. In adapting to the speed of new communication technologies, the end user, who is faster than rules and policies, is demonstrating constantly updated behavior models and methods in the processes of message reception, production, reproduction, evaluation and distribution. This rapid change and flexibility is a challenge, especially for management and regulators.

If we look at media literacy education in Uzbekistan, it can be seen that since the beginning of the 2000s, this issue has been accepted as a public policy and research field, and since 2017, attention has increased even more. At the same time, there are some problems in managing, regulating and putting into practice the theoretical work on this topic and the knowledge obtained from international platforms. These shortcomings are reflected in the seminars and meetings held, as well as in the results of field studies. Media education is an education that needs to be rapidly updated in the context of the changing era of future technology teachers, depending on the production mechanisms, and most importantly, to be integrated and used in different classes for application to different classes.

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